

Critical Big Data Literacy Tools – Engaging Citizens and Promoting Responsible Internet Usage

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Abstract

Datafied societies need *informed public debate* about the implications of data science technologies. At present, internet users are often unaware of the potential consequences of disclosing personal data online and few citizens have the knowledge to participate in such debates. This paper argues that critical big data literacy efforts are one way to address this lack of knowledge. The paper draws on findings from a small qualitative investigation of the effectiveness of online *critical big data literacy tools*. Through pre and post use testing, the short- and longer-term influence of these tools on people’s privacy attitudes and behaviour was investigated.

The research showed that the tools tested had a predominantly positive initial effect, leading to *improved critical big data literacy* among participants, which resulted in *more privacy-sensitive attitudes* and *internet usage*. When analysing the tools’ longer-term influence, results were more mixed, with evidence suggesting for some that literacy effects of the tools were *short-lived* while for others, they led to more *persistent and growing literacy*. Research findings confirm previous research noting the *complexity of privacy attitudes* and also find that *resignation* towards privacy is multi-faceted. Overall, this study *reaffirms the importance* of critical big data literacy and produces new findings about the value of interactive data literacy tools. These tools have been under-researched to date. This research shows that these tools provide a significant means to work toward empowering internet users, promoting responsible internet usage and ideally enabling more citizens to engage in public debates about changing data systems.

Keywords – Critical Data Literacy; Critical Digital Literacy; Online Privacy Attitudes; Digital Resignation; Critical Data Studies

1 Introduction

Given the ever-growing relevance of big data and automated systems in all areas of society, many argue that we have entered an age of “datafication” (e.g. Mayer-Schönberger & Cukier, 2013; Gray et al., 2018; Hintz et al., 2018; Redden, 2018). With private companies and govern-

ments worldwide collecting and analysing vast amounts of – among others – personal data and the use of automated systems increasing rapidly, there has been a “profound transformation in how society is ordered, decisions are made, and citizens are monitored through ‘big data’” (Hintz et al., 2018, p.2f). Academic research has challenged these systems’ “aura of truth, objectivity, and accuracy” (boyd & Crawford, 2012, p.663) and has highlighted how these systems can be used to profile, target and socially sort citizens in ways that can affect their financial circumstances, ability to find employment, and access to essential services (e.g. O’Neil, 2016; Redden & Brand, 2017; Eubanks, 2018). As large-scale data collection and related algorithmic systems increasingly transform the public sector, a critical public debate about data practices is essential.

However, few citizens have the knowledge to participate in such debates. Recent research has repeatedly emphasised a knowledge gap of American, European and German internet users on data, algorithms and online privacy (Turow et al., 2018; Grzymek & Puntschuh, 2019; Müller-Peters, 2019). For example, one study identified a “major understanding gap around technologies” with a quarter of British having “no idea how internet companies make their money” (Doteveryone, 2018, p.5). This emphasises that while users may be aware of data collection practices, they often only have a vague idea of how “‘the system’—the opaque under-the-hood predictive analytics regimes that they know are tracking their lives but to which they have no access” is operating (Turow et al., 2015, p.20). Despite such vague knowledge, research shows that many consumers are uncomfortable with algorithmic practices (e.g. Bucher, 2017; Miller et al., 2018; Müller-Peters, 2019).

Consequently, more and more scholars are calling for greater efforts to educate people about big data (Müller-Peters, 2019), investing in “new forms of public engagement and education” (Doteveryone, 2018, p.6) and increasing the public’s *literacy* about big data practices (e.g. Turow et al., 2018; Grzymek & Puntschuh, 2019). Yet, there is still a lack of literacy efforts, too little

knowledge on what kind of literacy efforts work best and a lack of constructive or comprehensive research on how to address people's lacking knowledge.

2 Critical Big Data Literacy

As a response to this gap in research, this study suggests addressing this lack of knowledge and understanding through *critical big data literacy*. This concept combines approaches from three key fields of research: First, *Critical Data Studies* aim to understand the “importance of data” (Kitchin & Lauriault, 2014, p.2) and examine the critical effects of datafication on individuals, society, industry and governance. This work builds on the premise that data and algorithms are never as neutral as they seem (e.g. Dalton & Thatcher, 2014; Zuboff, 2015; O’Neil, 2016; Kitchin, 2017; Eubanks, 2018). Secondly, concepts of *critical media and digital literacy* originate in the field of education and pedagogy and aim to improve people’s knowledge and skills of (digital) media (e.g. Hammer, 2011; Hinrichsen & Coombs, 2013; Garcia et al., 2015; Pangrazio, 2016). However, aspects related to big data systems are rarely mentioned. Thirdly, the small and emerging field of *data literacy* research predominantly employs an active and creative understanding of such literacy (e.g. Frank et al., 2016; Carretero et al., 2017; D’Ignazio, 2017; Khan et al., 2018). Some concepts include a critical reflection of big data practices either while or as a result of working with data, yet this is often restricted to classroom or workshop environments (e.g. D’Ignazio & Bhargava, 2015; Crusoe, 2016; Hautea et al., 2017; François & Monteiro, 2018; Gray et al., 2018).

Based on this, I argue that there is more involved in data literacy, particularly in a datafied society, than is often included in existing literacy approaches. Thus, I suggest being *critically data literate* means to be *aware of* and able to *critically reflect* upon *big data collection practices, data uses and the possible risks and implications* that come with these practices, as well as being capable of *implementing this knowledge for a more responsible internet usage*. Particularly the last two aspects of a critical reflection of the general system of data collection and analysis as well as the ability to implement this understanding into one’s everyday usage of digital technologies constitute aspects that are missing in most existing literacy approaches.

This small in-depth qualitative study examined examples of existing efforts to promote such literacy – *critical big data literacy tools* – and their influence on internet users’ concern for privacy and their internet usage in the short and longer term.

Accordingly, the study is also informed by privacy research. Despite being a highly ambiguous concept which is often measured in different ways, most results on people’s privacy attitudes are consistent in showing their

general concern for privacy (Marreiros et al., 2017, p.2). Explanatory models for the nevertheless widespread disclosure of personal data online – a controversial inconsistency often referred to as the ‘privacy paradox’ (e.g. Kokolakis, 2017, p.122) – include the idea of a rational cost-benefit analysis (e.g. Westin, 2003; Draper, 2017); people’s poor knowledge (Turow et al., 2014; see also above); and notions of a resignation towards privacy (Hargittai & Marwick, 2016; Dencik & Cable, 2017; Draper & Turow, 2019). These findings informed my research design and instruments.

3 Methodology

In order to identify existing examples for critical big data literacy tools, this study used a snowball sampling method starting with the interactive web-series ‘Do Not Track’ (Upian et al., 2015). Through following links and mentions in each episode, the original sample of exemplary tools was compiled. By using visual mapping techniques and conducting a comparative analysis of the tools, a typology was developed. Through theory-driven selection criteria based on media literacy evaluation or effectiveness research (Bergsma & Carney, 2008; Hobbs, 2010; Burrows et al., 2013; Hindmarsh et al., 2015), three tools most suitable for this study were selected.¹

As a second step, these three tools’ influences on people’s privacy attitudes and behaviour were investigated through pre and post use testing. Using purposive sampling, ten participants were selected for this qualitative multi-methods study. As intended, the sample consisted of students with an ‘average’ digital literacy – i.e. using the internet regularly and being familiar with digital technologies without possessing any special previous knowledge about big data practices. Testing took place before using the tools, one week after the ‘intervention’ and finally eight months later. In the 40 minute ‘intervention’, the participants used the three selected tools and were also invited to additionally navigate freely around further links and resources they found. This free design aimed at catering for the needs of different learning types and allowing a natural browsing behaviour. To be able to reconstruct the resources used, how much time spent with each, and how people’s browsing behaviours differed, a screen recording tool was used. The participants’ initial reactions on the tools during and after the intervention were also observed, which allowed for additional insights. At each of the three points in time, questionnaires tested the participants’ concern for privacy as well as various aspects

¹ Upian et al. (2015). Do Not Track. <https://donottrack-doc.com/en/> ; Tactical Technology Collective (no date). Me and My Shadow. <https://myshadow.org> ; La Quadrature du Net (2014). Reclaim Our Privacy. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TnDd5JmNFXE>.

of their internet usage – representing their ‘privacy behaviour’. The concern for privacy was measured using 19 statements about privacy and data protection, which were conceptualised around different topics and designed building on established instruments that measure privacy attitudes and concerns, adapting these instruments according to this study’s research question (Smith et al., 1996; Malhotra et al., 2004; Chellappa & Sin, 2005). Moreover, the questionnaires included open questions in order to invite participants to reflect on the tools used. Finally, qualitative one-hour interviews with five participants were conducted eight months after the intervention. These aimed at a more in-depth understanding of people’s concern for privacy, the changes made to their internet usage, their reflections on the tools and a clarification of ambiguities that arose before. The interviews were structured around an interview guide, which was adapted to the individual participant based on the prior findings.

4 Influences on Privacy Attitudes and Behaviour

Even though this study also revealed highly interesting findings on examples for existing critical big data literacy tools, design and content approaches they apply and the participants’ reflections on these tools’, this paper will focus on the study’s core question: The influence these tools have on people’s privacy attitudes and behaviour.² As outlined above, critical big data literacy includes more than mere knowledge about big data and thus is difficult to measure. In this study, this literacy was operationalised by investigating people’s internet usage and their concern for privacy. While these are likely insufficient variables to measure *all* aspects of critical big data literacy as outlined above, an increase in people’s concern for privacy and more privacy-sensitive internet usage certainly indicate a generally increased knowledge, understanding and critical reflection as well as the ability to implement these concerns into one’s daily internet usage.

4.1 The Positive Influence of Critical Big Data Literacy Tools

Overall, this study found a positive influence of the critical big data literacy tools in fostering critical big data literacy, which resulted in an increased concern about privacy and more privacy-sensitive internet usage of the participants. When examining the short-term impact of the tools one week after the intervention, firstly, an *increase in concern for privacy* for eight of the ten participants could be

measured. Secondly, all but two participants used the open text fields to emphasise their *perceived increase* in privacy awareness and concern. Thirdly, distinct changes in the participants’ *internet usage* could be identified. Half of the participants checked their privacy settings, many started to use ad and tracking blockers, restricted the use of location services, increased their number of passwords, several cleared their cookies and one even started to use the Tor Browser. Fourthly, the majority of participants used a final open text field to emphasise their newly gained awareness and understanding of big data and privacy, the critical view they developed through the tools and to express their *appreciation of this new literacy*.

While this first part of the study also showed some ambiguities, such as a decrease in measured concern for two participants, the overall finding of a positive influence was nevertheless unequivocal. When investigating the *longer-term influence* of the tools after eight months, some findings clearly reaffirmed this positive influence, yet no distinct general trend could be identified. The five participants who took part in this in-depth follow-up study showed *diverse longer-term developments*, yet the majority indicated an increased concern about at least *some aspects of privacy* (see 4.3) and all participants stated an increase of caution in at least *some situations of data disclosure online*. Moreover, several participants expressed a guilty conscience of not having done more.

However, despite the diversity of the findings, this follow-up study also provided strong evidence for a positive longer-term influence of the tools on people’s critical big data literacy. Two of the five participants showed very distinct changes in their privacy concern and behaviour, which not only remained, but even *intensified* in the months after using the tools. Both were very aware and concerned about the issue of privacy and the collection of their personal data online and have taken extensive measures to restrict their data disclosure online after using the tools. Both repeatedly emphasised the importance of more education on these issues and one even considered teaching data literacy in the future. Before taking part in the study, both participants had no special interest in or knowledge about online privacy but had a general curiosity about internet-related topics or a general drive to learn more. Importantly, both participants clearly linked the increase in their awareness and concern for privacy and the changes they made to their internet usage *directly to the tools* used in this study. This constitutes a highly suggestive outcome about the positive influence data literacy efforts can have.

Also the other participants whose privacy concerns and behaviours were examined in depth showed interesting longer-term developments. While two participants showed concern about *some aspects* of online privacy, the sample also included one case of ‘defaulting back’ to their original

² More detailed findings on these tools, their content and design approaches and the participants’ suggestions for prospective tools are being prepared for publication.

attitude and behaviour. This participant had a very strong initial reaction to the tools, which they described as: “Oh my goodness, everyone knows everything about me, I need to delete myself.” However, while this strong reaction led to a few initial small changes in their internet usage, this attitude faded with time and did not lead to a lasting change in privacy concern or behaviour.

Thus, examining the influence of critical big data literacy tools on people’s privacy attitudes and their internet usage led to evidence of an *only short-lived effect* of the tools as well as a *persistent and even growing* increase in concern for privacy, expressed in attitude and actions.

4.2 Reasoning and Motivations behind Changes

In the second stage of the study, some patterns emerged that hinted at the participants’ reasonings when making changes to their internet usage. For example, they seemed hesitant to make changes to the e-mail providers and instant messengers they used, but made various other, lower-threshold changes. These patterns of *convenience* and a *network effect* could be clearly confirmed through the qualitative interviews in the third stage of the study. Many participants directly referred to these notions as a reasoning for their attitudes but also as strong motivators for making decisions on their internet usage. Overall, this analysis repeatedly found a *discrepancy* between the envisaged ‘ideal state’ of privacy versus the more difficult implementation of this into reality. The notions of convenience and the network effect are examples of this discrepancy. While many participants of this study emphasised their concern for privacy, they also explained being drawn by the convenience of, for example, personalisation mechanisms or felt unable to change their internet usage because their friends and family were not willing to. Moreover, both the two very concerned participants but even those who seemed unconcerned at first glance expressed a *guilty conscience* about their lacking concern or activism when asked further.

Besides, new and unexpected notions could be identified. *Security concerns* constituted a strong justification for certain behaviours online and some participants expressed having *given up on protecting certain data* and focussing on restricting the collection of other data instead. Further, many still feel *unable to protect their privacy* online and call for easier means of data protection. Interestingly, these arguments correspond with this study’s findings on the complexity of privacy concerns, which identified a prevalence of concern about *data security* as well as further evidence for a *resignation* towards privacy (see 4.3). Finally, what nearly all participants agreed on and strongly emphasised was that the problematic aspects of big data systems are currently *too removed from*

individuals and that the protection of one’s data online should be *made easier*.

4.3 Complexity of Privacy Concerns

As already indicated above, this study clearly confirmed the complexity of people’s privacy concerns. Categorising the participants’ privacy attitudes into ‘concerned’ or ‘not concerned’ proved difficult as they were often only worried about certain aspects of online privacy, seemed unconcerned but then expressed a guilty conscience or a resignation towards their online privacy, or they explained being torn between concern and convenience. While an elaborate discussion of the often contradictory and fluctuating nature of these concerns cannot be provided in this paper, the following paragraph gives a first overview of these findings, which will be discussed in more detail in the future.

Overall, *nuanced themes* emerged both in relation to a concern about privacy but also with regards to a feeling of not ‘being bothered’ by online privacy. Interestingly, many participants expressed concern but nevertheless felt *unable to imagine specific negative consequences* of data disclosure online. Apart from this and further *contradictions within* the individual participants’ privacy attitudes, also *distinct differences between* the five participants’ understandings of privacy could be identified. Moreover, the findings outlined above suggest the notion of *different dimensions of online privacy*, such as a prevalent concern about the primarily technological issue of *data security*; less common worries about the *impact* data disclosure might have, such as tracking, scoring or surveillance; but also concern about *personal security* and the *social implications* of data-driven technologies. Finally, the notion of *resignation* was examined in more depth. The feeling of having ‘given up’ on one’s data was discussed by several participants and one particularly elaborated on the *origin* of the feeling as well as suggesting possible *solutions* to prevent resignation in the future.

5 Engaging Citizens and Promoting Responsible Internet Usage

Overall, this paper argues that the researched tools promote critical big data literacy. While not without ambiguities, the study’s findings showed a predominantly strong initial reaction to the tools leading to more concern for privacy and more privacy-sensitive internet usage. When analysing the longer-term influence of the tools, results are more mixed with evidence of both a short-lived effect of the tools for some and also of a significant longer-term impact for others. The differences between participants could be attributed to individual characteristics such as a general curiosity or interest in the area. However, more research is

required in order to better understand factors that determine the longer-term success of data literacy efforts. Moreover, this study's findings confirmed the theory that people might know about the collection of their data online, yet they have little awareness and understanding of the implications the disclosure of their data might have. Together with the many calls for more education on big data systems both from researchers and from this study's participants, this clearly emphasises the importance of critical big data literacy and the necessity for more research in this field. One key message of this study is that this literacy seems to not only empower internet users and constitute an important asset of contemporary citizenship but is also highly appreciated by the participants themselves. Even though the study showed that privacy concerns are incredibly complex and often restricted to certain aspects of online privacy, the participants were predominantly concerned when learning more about the use of their data. At least in the context of this very small sample, this outcome debunks claims of the indifferent internet user, who does not care about privacy and feels like they have 'nothing to hide'.

Thus, this study advances research on people's knowledge of data collection and analysis practices, but also on attitudes towards privacy. The complexity of privacy concerns was repeatedly confirmed and the different understandings and aspects of privacy, such as a prevalence of data security issues or a discrepancy between people's envisaged 'ideal state' of privacy versus the more difficult implementation of this into reality need to be considered and better understood through future research. Moreover, the study contributes in-depth findings to the small existing body of research on digital resignation by considering potential origins as well as possible solutions for a resignation towards privacy.

Finally, this research provided valuable in-depth findings on people's data literacy and a first insight into the influence of critical big data literacy tools on people's privacy concern and behaviour. With the increasing datafication of the public sector, it is essential to address public concerns, foster digital trust and enable citizens to protect their data online. Despite its small scale and some ambiguities in the findings, the research clearly shows that these not previously researched critical big data literacy tools provide a significant means to work toward empowering internet users, promoting responsible internet usage and ideally enabling more citizens to engage in public debates about changing data systems. More theoretical and empirical research on the concept of critical big data literacy, the implementation of such literacy into practice and on existing tools is required. This study provides various leverage points to address this gap in research. It also became clear that more education on big data systems is necessary and the protection of personal

data online needs to be made easier. Thus, besides more research, also more resources to teach critical big data literacy are required. My future work will present first suggestions on 'what works' in terms of such tools' design and content strategies.

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